

Decisive Data using Multi-Modality Optical Sensors for Advanced Vehicular Systems

Muhammad Ali Farooq¹, Waseem Shariff¹, Mehdi Sefidgar Dilmaghani¹, Wang Yao¹, Moazam Soomro², and Peter Corcoran¹

¹*School of Engineering, University of Galway, Ireland*

²*College of Engineering and Computer Science, University of Central Florida, USA*

Abstract

Optical sensors have played pivotal role in acquiring real world data for critical applications. This data when integrated with advanced machine learning algorithms provides meaningful information thus enhancing human vision. This paper focuses on various optical technologies for design and development of state-of-the-art out-cabin forward vision systems and in-cabin driver monitoring systems. The focused optical sensors include Long Wave Thermal Imaging (LWIR) cameras, Near Infrared (NIR), Neuromorphic/event cameras, Visible CMOS cameras and Depth cameras. Further the paper discusses different potential applications which can be employed using the unique strengths of each these optical modalities in real time environment.

Keywords: LWIR, NIR, Event Cameras, Imaging, Image Processing, Machine Vision.

1 Introduction

Advanced vehicular systems rely on various optical modalities and hardware sensors to enhance driver safety, vehicles efficiency, and performance. Most common key technologies which are directly associated with next generation autonomous vehicles [Automotive, 2022] includes.

- **Camera Vision Systems:** Camera-based vision systems capture visual information from inside the vehicle and the vehicle's surroundings. They are used for in cabin applications such as adjusting car internal temperature adjustment according to driver and occupant requirements, lane departure warning, traffic sign recognition, pedestrian detection, and object tracking [Farooq et al., 2021], [Jia et al., 2008].
- **Head-Up Display (HUD) and Augmented Reality (AR):** HUD projects important information, such as speed, navigation instructions, and alerts, onto the windshield or a dedicated display unit. It makes easy for the driver to access vital information without taking their eyes off the road, enhancing safety and situational awareness. [Charissis and Papanastasiou, 2010]. Similarly AR can be used in vehicle windshields to overlay digital information, such as navigation cues, traffic data, and safety warnings, onto the real-world view. This technology enhances driver assistance and provides a more intuitive driving experience [Wang et al., 2020].
- **Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) Communication:** V2X communication enables vehicles to exchange information with other vehicles, infrastructure, and pedestrians. Optical communication systems, such as visible light communication (VLC), is used to transmit data between vehicles or from traffic signals, enabling real-time cooperative driving, collision avoidance, and traffic management [Wang et al., 2019].

Keeping this in view in this study we will mainly discuss various camera technologies along with their respective strengths and weakness to elaborate their importance in challenging environmental and atmospheric conditions for advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS) and driver monitoring systems (DMS). Further we have highlighted the importance of machine learning algorithms to extract meaningful and decisive information that can aid drivers in real time driving experience.

2 Optical Sensor Technologies and Applications for Vehicular Systems

In this work we have mainly focused camera vision systems that can effectively employed and integrated with existing vehicular automation systems.

2.1 Visible CMOS Cameras

CMOS (complementary metal oxide semiconductor) camera is a digital camera that uses a CMOS image sensor, which is a device that converts light into an electrical signal. Generally, CMOS consists of the following parts: microlenses, color filters, metal lines, photodiodes, and substrates. CMOS cameras have several advantages compared with traditional CCD (charge-coupled device) cameras, including low power consumption, fast readout speeds, high integration, and low cost. These features allow CMOS cameras to be used in a variety of applications as follows.

- **Vehicle Detection and Tracking:** CMOS cameras are used to detect and position vehicles [He and Zhou, 2021] on the road. The captured images or video streams are analyzed by image processing and computer vision algorithms to identify and track vehicles on the road [Do and Yoo, 2019] for traffic monitoring, vehicle counting, and vehicle speed measurement.
- **Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS):** CMOS cameras are integral components of ADAS, which is used to warn drivers of any possible hazards on the road including lane departure warnings, forward collision warnings, pedestrian detection, and traffic sign recognition. These cameras capture the road ahead and provide real-time data to ADAS algorithms [Kuo et al., 2011], enabling the system to detect and provide assistance to the driver, which is important for improving traffic safety and preventing accidents.
- **Autonomous Vehicle Navigation:** CMOS cameras play a crucial role in autonomous vehicle navigation [Liu et al., 2008]. They provide visual input to the autonomous driving system, allowing the vehicle to understand its surroundings, detect and track other vehicles, and make decisions based on the detected objects and their trajectories.
- **Traffic Signal Control:** CMOS cameras can be used in traffic signal control systems to automatically adjust signal timing and dispensing by monitoring vehicle flow [Liu et al., 2012] and traffic conditions on the road in real-time to optimize traffic flow and reduce congestion.

Thus, CMOS cameras play a vital role in vehicular systems, providing efficient and accurate image acquisition and processing capabilities, supporting traffic monitoring, safety management, traffic flow analysis, and other applications, and contributing to traffic management and road safety.

2.2 LWIR Thermal Camera

LWIR (Long-Wave Infrared) cameras, also known as thermal infrared cameras, are designed to capture thermal radiation emitted by objects. They operate in the long-wave infrared spectrum covering the wavelengths ranging from 8 μ m to 14 μ m (8,000 to 14,000nm). Since LWIR cameras work by detecting the thermal infrared radiations also referred to as heat patterns, these cameras do not rely on external lighting conditions which makes them ideal for low lighting scenarios and even zero lighting conditions. The key applications of these cameras are as follows.

- **Night Vision:** LWIR cameras can capture images in total darkness or low-light conditions. This feature makes them perfect choice for external roadside environmental monitoring by integrating these cameras with deep learning-based algorithms. We can find various published studies elaborating its extensive usage for external object detection [Farooq et al., 2021], object tracking, and lane detection [Farooq et al., 2023b].
- **Vision in Adverse Conditions:** LWIR cameras are less affected by factors like smoke, fog, dust, or poor visibility caused by environmental conditions. They can penetrate certain materials and provide visibility in situations where conventional CMOS based visible cameras are unable to produce robust results. This feature allows the drivers to get comprehensive roadside thermal perception even in harsh weather conditions.
- **Temperature Measurement:** LWIR cameras enable non-contact temperature measurement. They can accurately measure the temperature of objects, even in challenging environments or from a distance. This capability is valuable feature for in cabin application such as driver and occupant temperature monitoring thus adjusting internal temperature of the car. Moreover, this feature can be useful for drivers' drowsiness and fatigue detection thus generating timely alerts to avoid traffic collisions.

Figure 1 shows the out-cabin object detection results on various thermal frames acquired from publicly available thermal datasets [Farooq et al., 2023a].

Figure 1: Thermal Imaging Frames with Out-cabin Object Detection Results

2.3 NIR Camera

NIR (Near-Infrared) thermal cameras, also referred to as SWIR (Short-Wave Infrared) thermal cameras, can acquire thermal radiation in the near-infrared spectrum, typically ranging from 0.9 μm to 1.7 μm wavelength spectrum. Likewise, LWIR thermal cameras NIR cameras offer non-contact temperature measurement, and vision through obscuring elements. These features make them optimal choice for different in-cabin and out-cabin vehicular applications such as monitoring driver's attentiveness, detect signs of drowsiness or distraction, and issue alerts and timely warnings. Moreover, NIR cameras can monitor the interior environment of the vehicle as shown in the figure 2. They can detect the presence of occupants, their seating positions, and activity levels. This information can be utilized for personalized climate control, optimizing airbag deployment, or triggering alerts in case of unattended passenger such as children.

Figure 2: NIR output for monitoring the driver and passenger

2.4 Neuromorphic Sensors

Neuromorphic sensors, also known as event cameras, have a unique way of capturing scenes. Unlike traditional RGB cameras that capture multiple frames per second, event cameras have independent pixels that only respond

to changes in light, resulting in a stream of events rather than continuous images. Each event includes a timestamp, the pixel's position, and a binary polarity indicating an increase or decrease in light. This type of camera offers advantages such as speed, low memory usage, fewer computations, and privacy preservation, making it ideal for autonomous driving [Graça et al., 2023, Chen et al., 2020]. This research focuses on discussing the in-cabin and out-of-cabin vision applications of event cameras in the automotive industry.

- **In-cabin applications:** The event camera's high temporal resolution makes it an excellent choice for applications such as monitoring driver drowsiness in vehicles. Traditional cameras struggle to track subtle facial expressions, blink counting, head pose/gaze estimation, and saccadic movement analysis, which are crucial for assessing drowsiness levels. By utilizing event cameras, vehicles can move closer to achieving full autonomy. Researchers propose new algorithms to monitor drivers, analyze key factors in drowsiness, and address challenges in event camera-based monitoring systems [Ryan et al., 2021, Dilmaghani et al., 2022]. One approach involves using a LSTM-based system that detects driver distraction by creating 3D tensors from event camera output streams [Yang et al., 2022]. Another algorithm focuses on detecting yawning, an important indicator of drowsiness, using frames generated from event streams [Kielty et al., 2023].
- **Out-cabin applications:** Pedestrian detection is crucial for autonomous driving and various approaches have been proposed. In [Wan et al., 2021], a YOLO-v3 based architecture is suggested to detect pedestrians from frames generated by integrating event streams. Another study [Ojeda et al., 2020] introduces a hardware-efficient architecture using event streams, consisting of denoising the input stream and a simple neural network for pedestrian detection. Object detection is also important in next generation automobiles, with [Wzorek and Kryjak, 2022] using YOLO-v4 to detect traffic signs, [Shariff et al., 2022] presenting a proof of concept for YOLO-based forward perception systems, and [Mentasti et al., 2022] proposing two event-based solutions for object detection and tracking in traffic monitoring, one based on geometrical schemes and the other on neural networks.

Figure 3: Event camera output samples: a) in-cabin driver monitoring [Ryan et al., 2021], b) out-cabin road side object detection [Shariff et al., 2022]

2.5 Depth Cameras

Depth cameras, also known as 3D cameras or depth sensing cameras, are a type of sensor used in automotive applications to capture depth information of the surrounding environment. These cameras operate by emitting infrared (IR) or laser light and measuring the time it takes for the light to bounce back after hitting objects in the scene. By analysing the stereo vision, time-of-flight or structured light patterns, depth cameras can create a three-dimensional representation of the scene [Khan et al., 2022, Khan et al., 2023, Kumar et al., 2020]. In the context of automotive, depth cameras offer several key features and benefits:

- **Object Detection with Depth Sensing:** Depth cameras provide accurate depth information, allowing for precise detection of moving objects. This enables advanced driver-assistance systems (ADAS) and autonomous vehicles to identify and monitor the position, size, and movement of pedestrians, vehicles, and

Figure 4: Depth Camera Sensor Outputs. a) In-cabin RGB camera b) Corresponding in-cabin depth output c) Out-cabin RGB camera d) Corresponding out-cabin depth output.

other obstacles on the road. This information is crucial for making real-time decisions and ensuring safe driving [Zhou et al., 2022].

- **Distance Measurement:** Depth cameras enable accurate measurement of distances between the vehicle and objects in the surrounding environment. This information is essential for adaptive cruise control systems, automatic braking systems, and parking assistance, as it helps determine the appropriate response or manoeuvre required to maintain a safe distance from other vehicles or objects [Kumar et al., 2020].
- **Scene Understanding and Mapping:** Depth cameras provide a detailed representation of the scene, allowing vehicles to understand the geometry and structure of the environment. This helps in creating high-definition maps, path planning, and navigation, especially in complex urban environments or during adverse weather conditions where traditional sensors may struggle [Mehrzed, 2023].
- **Gesture and Occupant Recognition:** Depth cameras can be utilized for driver monitoring and gesture recognition inside the vehicle. By analysing the depth information, these cameras can track the driver's gaze, head position, and hand movements, enabling features such as driver drowsiness detection, distraction monitoring, and intuitive in-car controls through gestures [Leu et al., 2011].
- **Enhanced Safety and Collision Avoidance:** The depth information captured by these cameras enhances overall safety by providing a more comprehensive understanding of the environment. This enables the development of collision avoidance systems that can detect potential hazards and take proactive measures to prevent accidents [Ding and Su, 2023].
- **Low-Light Performance:** Like LWIR thermal cameras, some depth cameras are designed to work in low-light conditions. They use active illumination, such as infrared light, to capture depth information, making them suitable for driving scenarios with limited visibility or at night [Saxena et al., 2008].

By combining depth information with other sensor data, such as radar and LiDAR, depth cameras contribute to a comprehensive perception system for autonomous vehicles. They enable accurate and robust scene understanding, enhancing the safety, efficiency, and overall driving experience in automotive applications.

3 Discussion

This section will summarize the potential advantages of different optical modalities along with their weaknesses in automotive scenarios.

- The visible CMOS sensor provides high-resolution images in good external lighting conditions however the performance of these cameras is severely affected in low-light conditions. The LWIR thermal camera excels in low-light and even in zero-lighting situations by detecting thermal signatures. The NIR camera enhances visibility in low-light, while thermal cameras outperform NIR cameras in complete darkness. The event camera aids in real-time object tracking with low-latency imaging, while the depth camera focuses on depth sensing and is not optimized for night vision.

- For object detection, the visible CMOS sensor enables precise object recognition and classification with its high-resolution color imagery. In challenging lighting conditions, the LWIR thermal camera surpasses visible light cameras by detecting objects based on their thermal emissions. While the NIR camera is capable of object detection, thermal cameras generally outperform NIR cameras due to their ability to sense thermal signatures. The event camera, although primarily designed for real-time tracking, can contribute to overall perception systems by providing valuable visual information. Additionally, the depth camera can offer additional in-depth information, assisting in the identification of objects.
- In terms of facial recognition, the visible CMOS sensor may struggle in low-light conditions, while the LWIR thermal camera primarily captures thermal information rather than detailed facial features. The NIR camera is well-suited for facial recognition in low-light scenarios, capturing detailed facial features not easily visible to visible light cameras. The event camera's low-latency imaging capabilities can aid in real-time tracking of facial movements, and the depth camera can provide additional depth information for more accurate analysis of facial characteristics.
- For drowsiness and fatigue detection, the visible CMOS sensor has limited capability, while LWIR thermal cameras primarily capture thermal information rather than eye movements or facial features. NIR cameras are well-suited for monitoring driver drowsiness and fatigue due to their ability to analyze facial characteristics and detect eye movements even in low-light conditions. Event cameras have the potential to contribute to drowsiness and fatigue detection with their temporal information feature, but research in this area is limited. Additionally, depth cameras can provide additional depth information for a more comprehensive analysis of the driver's condition.
- In the domain of gesture recognition, the visible CMOS sensor can capture gestures but may require proper lighting conditions. LWIR thermal cameras excel in capturing thermal information but are not commonly used for gesture recognition. NIR cameras are well-suited for detailed hand movement capture, even in low-light conditions. Event cameras, with their low-latency imaging capabilities, contribute to real-time tracking of hand movements. Depth cameras, specifically designed for depth sensing, enable precise tracking of hand gestures for gesture recognition.
- When it comes to 3D mapping, the visible CMOS sensor has limited capability as it primarily captures color imagery without depth information. LWIR thermal cameras focus on capturing thermal information rather than depth and are not typically used for 3D mapping. Similarly, NIR cameras mainly capture color imagery without depth information and are not primarily used for 3D mapping. Event cameras provide valuable visual information for environment perception, while depth cameras, specifically designed for depth sensing, are ideal for creating accurate 3D maps of the vehicle's surroundings.

4 Conclusion and Future Work

In summary, the choice of optical sensor depends on the specific requirements for desired application in real-time environment. While visible CMOS sensors offer high-resolution colour imagery, thermal cameras excel in low-light and adverse weather conditions. NIR cameras provide enhanced visibility in low-light situations, event cameras offer real-time tracking capabilities, and depth cameras enable accurate 3D mapping. To make the best choice, it's essential to consider factors such as cost, performance requirements, and the specific needs of the application. By carefully evaluating these factors, one can determine the most appropriate optical sensor that strikes the right balance between functionality and affordability. Ultimately, selecting the right sensor can significantly impact the effectiveness and efficiency of a given system or application. As the possible future directions the array of multi modality optical sensors can be deployed in parallel with conventional sensors which includes LIDAR and RADAR for achieving maximum benefits for in-cabin as well as out-cabin applications.

References

- [Automotive, 2022] Automotive, S. (2022). Synopsys automotive. <https://www.synopsys.com/automotive/autonomous-driving-levels.html> [Accessed: 31/05/2023].
- [Charissis and Papanastasiou, 2010] Charissis, V. and Papanastasiou, S. (2010). Human-machine collaboration through vehicle head up display interface. *Cognition, Technology & Work*, 12:41–50.
- [Chen et al., 2020] Chen, G., Cao, H., Conradt, J., Tang, H., Rohrbein, F., and Knoll, A. (2020). Event-based neuromorphic vision for autonomous driving: A paradigm shift for bio-inspired visual sensing and perception. *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, 37(4):34–49.
- [Dilmaghani et al., 2022] Dilmaghani, M. S., Shariff, W., Ryan, C., Lemley, J., and Corcoran, P. (2022). Control and evaluation of event cameras output sharpness via bias. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2210.13929*.
- [Ding and Su, 2023] Ding, I.-J. and Su, J.-L. (2023). Designs of human-robot interaction using depth sensor-based hand gesture communication for smart material-handling robot operations. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part B: Journal of Engineering Manufacture*, 237(3):392–413.
- [Do and Yoo, 2019] Do, T.-H. and Yoo, M. (2019). Visible light communication-based vehicle-to-vehicle tracking using cmos camera. *IEEE Access*, 7:7218–7227.
- [Farooq et al., 2021] Farooq, M. A., Corcoran, P., Rotariu, C., and Shariff, W. (2021). Object detection in thermal spectrum for advanced driver-assistance systems (adas). *IEEE Access*, 9:156465–156481.
- [Farooq et al., 2023a] Farooq, M. A., Shariff, W., and Corcoran, P. (2023a). Evaluation of thermal imaging on embedded gpu platforms for application in vehicular assistance systems. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles*, 8(2):1130–1144.
- [Farooq et al., 2023b] Farooq, M. A., Shariff, W., O’callaghan, D., Merla, A., and Corcoran, P. (2023b). On the role of thermal imaging in automotive applications: A critical review. *IEEE Access*, 11:25152–25173.
- [Graça et al., 2023] Graça, R., McReynolds, B., and Delbruck, T. (2023). Shining light on the dvs pixel: A tutorial and discussion about biasing and optimization. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2304.04706*.
- [He and Zhou, 2021] He, J. and Zhou, B. (2021). Vehicle positioning scheme based on visible light communication using a cmos camera. *Optics express*, 29(17):27278–27290.
- [Jia et al., 2008] Jia, Z., Balasuriya, A., and Challa, S. (2008). Vision based data fusion for autonomous vehicles target tracking using interacting multiple dynamic models. *Computer vision and image understanding*, 109(1):1–21.
- [Khan et al., 2022] Khan, F., Farooq, M. A., Shariff, W., Basak, S., and Corcoran, P. (2022). Towards monocular neural facial depth estimation: Past, present, and future. *IEEE Access*, 10:29589–29611.
- [Khan et al., 2023] Khan, F., Shariff, W., Farooq, M. A., Basak, S., and Corcoran, P. (2023). A robust lightweight fused-feature encoder-decoder model for monocular facial depth estimation from single images trained on synthetic data. *IEEE Access*.
- [Kielty et al., 2023] Kielty, P., Dilmaghani, M. S., Ryan, C., Lemley, J., and Corcoran, P. (2023). Neuromorphic sensing for yawn detection in driver drowsiness. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.02888*.
- [Kumar et al., 2020] Kumar, G. A., Lee, J. H., Hwang, J., Park, J., Youn, S. H., and Kwon, S. (2020). Lidar and camera fusion approach for object distance estimation in self-driving vehicles. *Symmetry*, 12(2):324.

- [Kuo et al., 2011] Kuo, Y.-C., Pai, N.-S., and Li, Y.-F. (2011). Vision-based vehicle detection for a driver assistance system. *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, 61(8):2096–2100.
- [Leu et al., 2011] Leu, A., Aiteanu, D., and Gräser, A. (2011). A novel stereo camera based collision warning system for automotive applications. In *2011 6th IEEE International Symposium on Applied Computational Intelligence and Informatics (SACI)*, pages 409–414. IEEE.
- [Liu et al., 2008] Liu, C., Chen, J., Xu, Y., and Luo, F. (2008). Intelligent vehicle road recognition based on the cmos camera. In *2008 IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference*, pages 1–5. IEEE.
- [Liu et al., 2012] Liu, Z., Lin, S., Li, K., and Dong, A. (2012). Traffic flow video detection system based on line scan cmos sensor. *Advanced Science Letters*, 7(1):478–483.
- [Mehrzed, 2023] Mehrzed, S. (2023). Optimization of a simultaneous localization and mapping (slam) system for an autonomous vehicle using a 2-dimensional light detection and ranging sensor (lidar) by sensor fusion.
- [Mentasti et al., 2022] Mentasti, S., Kambale, A. W., and Matteucci, M. (2022). Event-based object detection and tracking-a traffic monitoring use case. In *Image Analysis and Processing. ICIAP 2022 Workshops: ICIAP International Workshops, Lecce, Italy, May 23–27, 2022, Revised Selected Papers, Part II*, pages 95–106. Springer.
- [Ojeda et al., 2020] Ojeda, F. C., Bisulco, A., Kepple, D., Isler, V., and Lee, D. D. (2020). On-device event filtering with binary neural networks for pedestrian detection using neuromorphic vision sensors. In *2020 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*, pages 3084–3088. IEEE.
- [Ryan et al., 2021] Ryan, C., O’Sullivan, B., Elrasad, A., Cahill, A., Lemley, J., Kielty, P., Posch, C., and Perot, E. (2021). Real-time face & eye tracking and blink detection using event cameras. *Neural Networks*, 141:87–97.
- [Saxena et al., 2008] Saxena, A., Chung, S. H., and Ng, A. Y. (2008). 3-d depth reconstruction from a single still image. *International journal of computer vision*, 76:53–69.
- [Shariff et al., 2022] Shariff, W., Farooq, M. A., Lemley, J., and Corcoran, P. (2022). Event-based yolo object detection: Proof of concept for forward perception system. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2212.07181*.
- [Wan et al., 2021] Wan, J., Xia, M., Huang, Z., Tian, L., Zheng, X., Chang, V., Zhu, Y., and Wang, H. (2021). Event-based pedestrian detection using dynamic vision sensors. *Electronics*, 10(8):888.
- [Wang et al., 2019] Wang, J., Shao, Y., Ge, Y., and Yu, R. (2019). A survey of vehicle to everything (v2x) testing. *Sensors*, 19(2):334.
- [Wang et al., 2020] Wang, Z., Han, K., and Tiwari, P. (2020). Augmented reality-based advanced driver-assistance system for connected vehicles. In *2020 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)*, pages 752–759. IEEE.
- [Wzorek and Kryjak, 2022] Wzorek, P. and Kryjak, T. (2022). Traffic sign detection with event cameras and dcnn. In *2022 Signal Processing: Algorithms, Architectures, Arrangements, and Applications (SPA)*, pages 86–91. IEEE.
- [Yang et al., 2022] Yang, C., Liu, P., Chen, G., Liu, Z., Wu, Y., and Knoll, A. (2022). Event-based driver distraction detection and action recognition. In *2022 IEEE International Conference on Multisensor Fusion and Integration for Intelligent Systems (MFI)*, pages 1–7. IEEE.
- [Zhou et al., 2022] Zhou, D., Song, X., Fang, J., Dai, Y., Li, H., and Zhang, L. (2022). Context-aware 3d object detection from a single image in autonomous driving. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 23(10):18568–18580.